

BILATERAL ADHESIVE CAPSULITIS IN A 54-YEARS OLD MALE: A CASE REPORT

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Abstract

Introduction: Adhesive capsulitis (AC), commonly known as frozen shoulder, is typically unilateral and frequently associated with systemic conditions such as diabetes or thyroid disorders. Bilateral idiopathic presentation without identifiable underlying causes is rare and presents a clinical challenge.

Patient Information: A 54-year-old male journalist presented with a six-month history of bilateral shoulder pain and stiffness. There was no history of trauma, metabolic disorders, or systemic disease. Functional limitations included difficulty in grooming, dressing, and overhead activities.

Clinical Findings: Bilateral restriction in active and passive shoulder movements was observed: Flexion 70°, Abduction 60° (left) and 55° (right), External Rotation 15°, and Internal Rotation reaching lumbosacral spine. Neurological and reflex testing was normal.

Diagnostic Assessment: Positive Apley's scratch test, normal initial X-rays (later showing calcification), and normal laboratory tests (FBS, HbA1c, TSH) confirmed idiopathic bilateral AC at the frozen stage.

Therapeutic Intervention: The patient underwent a structured, three-phase physiotherapy program over four weeks including moist heat, pendulum exercises, Spencer techniques, Maitland mobilizations, active-assisted ROM, resistance band strengthening, and functional training.

Outcomes: At four weeks, significant improvements were noted: pain reduced (VAS 6/10 to 2/10), ROM increased (Flexion 130°, Abduction 110°, ER 40°, IR reaching T8), and the patient resumed independent daily activities.

Discussion: This case underscores a rare instance of idiopathic bilateral adhesive capsulitis in a patient without systemic illness. Conservative physiotherapy, initiated early and applied consistently, proved effective in restoring functional mobility and alleviating pain.

Conclusion: Idiopathic bilateral AC, though rare, can be effectively managed through individualized, evidence-based physiotherapy. Early recognition and structured intervention are vital in restoring functional independence.

INTRODUCTION

Adhesive capsulitis (AC), commonly known as frozen shoulder, is characterized by pain and progressive restriction in both active and passive range of motion (ROM) of the shoulder (1). progressive restrictions of active and passive range of motion (ROM) at glenohumeral joint, and can lead to joint mobility restrictions that lead to evidently impaired the shoulder complex functions(2) AC seems to start as an inflammatory process along with accompanying synovitis that progresses to a fibrotic contracture of the capsule at shoulder joint, Primary, or idiopathic adhesive capsulitis, an underlying etiology or associated condition cannot be identified and primary adhesive capsulitis affects about 2% to 5% of the overall population(2, 3) Frozen Shoulder (FS) characterized by a fibrotic inflammatory process of unknown origin, with the most prominent symptoms being pain, stiffness, and reduced joint mobility(4) International Society of Arthroscopy, Knee Surgery and Orthopedic Sports Medicine (ISAKOS) Upper Limb Committee classified FS into idiopathic primary and secondary AC, Primary AC occurs without any direct cause or identifiable trauma, though the patient may have conditions like diabetes mellitus (DM) or thyroid disorders that are associated with stiffness(5) On the other hand, secondary AC refers to joint stiffness resulting from a known underlying cause, such as trauma, infection, or inflammatory disorders(6) AC is described in three pathological stages, the freezing stage, the frozen stage, and the thawing stage. the predictable prevalence of FS is 3%-5% of the general population(7) The condition most frequently affects individuals aged 40-60 years and is typically unilateral. Bilateral involvement of FS is very rare, accounting for about 10% of the cases, and is often linked to systemic conditions such as diabetes or hypothyroidism, one clinical case is reported of bilateral nature of FS by Marin McElroy et al. in 2022, the age of the patient was 50 years but the patient were having a systemic disease of

hyperthyroidism (5, 8) This clinical case highlights a rare presentation of idiopathic bilateral adhesive capsulitis in a male 54 years patient with no history of diabetes and hypothyroidism, treated conservatively with physiotherapy in a resource-limited clinical setting.

Guideline/Methods: this case report is carried out as per CARE guidelines (for CAse Reports) (developed by an international group of experts to support an increase in the accuracy, transparency, and usefulness of case reports)

Presentation of Case:

A 54-year-old male, Journalist by profession presented to the Physical Therapy Out Patient Department (OPD) of the School of Health Sciences, Peshawar, with complaints of pain and stiffness in both shoulders for the past 6 months. The examination and assessment of the patient were done by Dr. Muhammad Atif (PT) and Dr. Faryal Javed (PT) under the supervision of Dr. Zakir Ullah In-charge physical therapy OPD. The case was presented in in-session presentation among Rehab Faculty and were found unique. As The symptoms developed gradually, without any reported trauma, systemic disease like Diabetes and thyroid disorders, or previous surgery. The patient experienced nocturnal pain and was unable to perform overhead tasks, grooming, or dressing without assistance.

Physical examination findings:

Active and passive Rang of Motion (ROM) was significantly restricted in both shoulders: Flexion: 70° (bilateral) Abduction: 60° and 55° on left and right shoulder respectively External Rotation: 15° (bilateral) Internal Rotation: Reaching to the lumbosacral spine. Tenderness noted over the anterior glenohumeral joints right glenohumeral (GH) were more effected than left side, bilateral Strength was moderately reduced due to pain and

stiffness, Neurological examination and upper limb reflexes were normal upon a thorough examination.

Diagnostic Workup:

Apley's stretched test were positive, the patient was unable to perform overhead activities, specifically external rotation and abduction were found limited on both sides. Shoulder X-rays were normal initially but calcifications found latter on, Laboratory tests (FBS, HbA1c, TSH) ruled out diabetes and thyroid dysfunction.

Diagnosis:

Bilateral idiopathic adhesive capsulitis (Stage II - Frozen phase of AC) Diagnosis were made upon clinical decision by the whole Rehab team.

Treatment Plan:

The patient was placed on 4-week physiotherapy program including: Phase I: Moist heat, pendulum exercises, spencer techniques were also applied along with Maitland mobilizations (Grades I-II) for pain management and maintenance and improvement in ROM, Phase II: Active-assisted ROM with wand and pulley exercises with isometrics, In Phase III the patient were provided: Resistance band strengthening, scapular stabilization, and functional training for complete restoration of the condition, the patient were found very supportive and exercise oriented.

Outcome:

At 4-week follow-up: Pain improved from Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) 6/10 to 2/10 ROM improved significantly that is Flexion: 130°, Abduction: 110°, ER: 40°, IR: Reaching mid-back i.e. easily scratching the thoracic spine (T8) The patient resumed independent performance of his daily activities

Discussion:

Bilateral frozen shoulder is relatively uncommon (10 percent cases with systematic pathologies like diabetes and thyroid disorders) and often poses diagnostic and therapeutic challenges.(9, 10) The condition typically progresses through three phases: freezing, frozen, and thawing. In this case, the patient of age 54 years presented during the frozen phase with symmetrical involvement, but without

any metabolic, endocrine, or traumatic etiology. Physical therapy is believed the mainstay of conservative treatment in adhesive capsulitis, particularly in the absence of structural damage or advanced fibrosis(10) The intervention focused on pain management, improvement in ROM, gradual mobilization, and strengthening. The use of Maitland mobilizations, spencer techniques combined with moist heat and patient-specific exercise progression, was effective in restoring of activities of daily life(11, 12) Although corticosteroid injections and surgical options exist for resistant cases, this case demonstrates that even bilateral cases can respond well to non-invasive/conservative treatment and are able to manage through physical therapy, if the provided treatment is initiated early and consistently monitored(12)

Conclusion:

This case report highlights very rare demonstration of bilateral adhesive capsulitis (10 Percent) in a middle-aged male patient of age 54 years without any identifiable systemic pathology or traumatic cause. Although unilateral adhesive capsulitis is relatively very common and well-studied previously, bilateral involvement presents unique challenges in both diagnosis and management due to its compounded impact on functional independence and quality of life. The patient in this case presented during the frozen stage of the condition, with significant restrictions in active and passive shoulder movement bilaterally, along with persistent pain affecting activities of daily living such as grooming, dressing, and overhead reaching. Through a thorough clinical examination and exclusion of metabolic conditions such as diabetes or thyroid dysfunction, a diagnosis of idiopathic bilateral adhesive capsulitis was established. This clinical case illustrates that conservative physical therapy management can be highly effective in treating bilateral idiopathic adhesive capsulitis, even in older patients without any systemic illness. A structured, phase-wise protocol combining mobilizations, spencer techniques, stretching, and strengthening yields substantial functional gains and pain relief. In conclusion, this case demonstrates that a structured and individualized physiotherapy approach can lead to substantial recovery in patients with bilateral

adhesive capsulitis, even in the absence of pharmacological or surgical interventions. Awareness, early referral, and consistent physiotherapeutic care remain the key pillars in managing such complex musculoskeletal cases effectively. In conclusion, this case demonstrates that a structured and individualized physiotherapy approach can lead to considerable recovery in patients with bilateral adhesive capsulitis, even in the absence of pharmacological or surgical interventions. Awareness, early referral, and consistent physiotherapeutic care remain the key pillars in managing such complex musculoskeletal cases effectively.

Recommendation:

For bilateral cases of FS, a comprehensive, phase-wise physiotherapy protocol, including joint mobilization techniques (Maitland grades I-II) combined with spencer techniques, active-assisted range of motion exercises, isometric and resistance training, and postural education is highly recommended to administer over 04-weeks period. As per the available evidences till date conservative physical therapy, non-invasive intervention led to significant improvements in pain levels, shoulder mobility, and functional independence. This case emphasizes several important clinical aspects like Early diagnosis and intervention play a critical role in optimizing outcomes, particularly in bilateral cases where functional limitations are more severe. In the absence of systemic pathology, idiopathic bilateral adhesive capsulitis is too rare, should be considered in patients presenting with symmetrical shoulder involvement and progressive stiffness. From a rehabilitation perspective, this case reinforces the value of evidence-based clinical reasoning, patient education, and therapist-guided exercise progression in achieving meaningful recovery. It also calls attention to the need for further clinical and experimental research and long-term outcome studies on bilateral adhesive capsulitis to better guide treatment algorithms and prognostic expectations.

Ethical Approval: This case report was conducted in accordance with institutional ethical guidelines. No experimental procedures were performed.

Sources of Funding: No financial support was received for this case report.

Consent:

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Author Contributions

Zakir Ullah: Case management, data collection, manuscript drafting, Review, supervision, clinical input

All authors of this article have read and approved the final manuscript.

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